

AUTOMATION OF PROCESSING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS.
AN EXAMPLE, THE AIRBUS 330/340

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1 FOREWORD

Composites usage in aerospace structures meant a certain revolution, as these made possible reducing the weight and preventing the corrosion and fatigue in such structures, this would not have been possible using aluminum alloys. However, nothing can be obtained for nothing, the price to be paid for such a weight reduction is a considerable cost increase, both in the raw material and the labor.

The designs with metallic thinking and manufacturing with craftsmanship methods involve high costs for the completed structure.

The way to reduce the price of the composite structures is making a good design conforming the structural requirements manufacturing using advanced methods, a good management of materials to reduce the cost of the raw materials and the productive process automation.

This automation includes all of the stages, from the design using CAD systems, tooling design and manufacturing with the same information source that handles the design department, part manufacturing and inspection thereof with the design generated data.

Here we will cover the application of this automation process to carbon fiber/epoxy parts by means of ply lay-up and autoclave processing. Usage of other manufacturing processes that can be automated, e.g.: RTM, RIM, PULTRUSION are beyond the contents of this discussion, but development and application thereof in the aerospace structures area is getting a great deal of acceptance.

2 PRODUCTIVE PROCESSES AND AUTOMATION

The composite manufacturing also offers the possibility of building different parts, such as stiffeners, joining cleats, etc., into a single part, thus minimizing the number of parts to be assembled in a completed structure, therefore reducing the cost of the assembly thereof.

In addition to detail parts manufacturing, assembly thereof should be automated, designing with new joining procedures that can be automated.

The automation involves the nuancing of the following items.

- a) Every automation involves a great investment in equipment and tooling, which might make it unprofitable. A considerable manufacturing time saving and a minimum production rate are required to allow implementation of any automated process.
- b) Every automation involves that the part to be manufactured is automatable, i.e., the design should be made knowing the whole part manufacturing process, otherwise the cost associated to the automation rockets.
- c) When a process is automated, the material waste should be evaluated, as this is a very important issue due to the high price of the raw material.
- d) When automating, another issue to evaluate is the work in process capital, as the high financial costs force minimizing the stock of parts in process.

3 MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

The composite materials call out different manufacturing processes. Sometimes specific machines are required (spinning, winding, etc.), whereas other ones allow adoption of conventional machines or processes (cold pressing, hot pressing, etc.). Thus, the machinery used in the fabric manufacturing industry, quite automated, is being transformed for this type of processes (pattern cutting machines, stitching, etc.).

The most used processes in aerospace manufacturing with thermosetting matrix materials are two: contact molding, with all of its variances, and filament winding molding. The first one allows a wider range of variation in the more or less sophisticated geometrical shapes, whereas the second one allow closed structures manufacturing, maintaining the reinforcement materials continuity.

The contact process is the most used to manufacture primary structures by laying up plies, these being made up by tape, fabric or an hybrid thereof, located with different orientations. This process can be segregated into two different groups. Fig. 1.

The first group is representative of those processes before curing, and the second one with the part cured. The cure process is like a fence between both groups, wherein the philosophy to be applied to each of them is quite different. Thus, the technic in the second group are not quite different from those used for the conventional materials, except for the cutting speeds, cutters, and variables which are different for metal and non-metal items.

However, when the uncured material is considered, the manufacturing technology is quite different from the conventional one, requiring the operations in this group the main technical efforts to find systems, mechanical at least, to allow reaching the integrated production cells construction, removing the manual operations. In general, this group reaches 60 to 90% of the hours required to manufacture one part.

Fabric and tape preimpregnated materials are used for the contact manufacturing process. These materials are procured in rolls, wherein the fibers, either woven with different patterns of unidirectionally aligned, are encapsulated in a polymer resin matrix. Because of this reason, they must be stored under special conditions and in refrigerators with temperatures of -25°C, featuring a limited life time under such conditions (ranging between 6 months and 1 year) and a number of usage hours at temperatures of $22 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ (300 hours as an average).

The following is a summary of the machining and automation status in the manufacturing of composite laminated structure parts or assemblies using the onctact method, and later on, C.A.S.A. development to manufacture primary structures, highlighting that of the A-330/340 Horizontal tail plane skin is subsequently discussed, this is the first fuel tank made in composite for the civil commercial aircraft.

It is interesting pointing out that even though some aircraft or aircraft components manufacturing companies have machine, automated or even robotized processes, there is a long way ahead, as it is necessary attaining integration of all of those units, quite often isolated, without continuity between each other. That is, integration of all of the is necessary to reach the CIM concept. For this purpose, it is not only necessary machining or automating each operation, but the location in the productive process lay-up has to have been thought about. It therefore is necessary that the foundations wherein the facilities are to be located should be prepared for this purpose.

4 STATE OF THE ART OF THE BASIC OPERATIONS

The basic operations required to manufacture a part are shown in Figures 1 and 2. The latter shows some of the most essential conditions for these operations.

4.1 Storage

Preimpregnated materials, as stated above, are stored in refrigerators, and subsequently issued to the production areas. Traditionally, this is a process requiring one man taking the roll out of the refrigerator and moving it to the cutting or molding clean areas using fork lifts.

Automation if this process is not to be justified by the labor reduction or capability increase, but basing on the following concepts:

- a) Human error prevention in the material selection.
- b) Orderly material storage.
- c) Material life control.
- d) Preventing safety and hygiene problems.
- e) Possibility to incorporate the raw material, since received in the plant, into an integrated manufacturing cell.

The storage system is quite similar to that used in the conventional industry, except for the necessity to keep the material at -25°C during storage thereof.

4.2 Material Cutting (Fig. 3)

Cutting of the preimpregnated materials, which is usually performed by hand, is slow, awkward and subjected to human errors. This method uses blades and scissors as tools, the cutting paths of which are obtained by means of a ruler, set square and templates. It features the great disadvantage of having the number of plies to be cut at the same time quite limited.

The ply die cutting process provides a great cutting capability for that area limited by the size of the table. The most important problem is that any design change concerning the plies geometry involves construction of new dies.

The automated cutting system ("computer controlled ply cutting and labelling"/"reciprocating knife") consists in a cutting table, above which there is a numerically controlled cutting head. The desired geometry is directly input into the control as the cutting tool path, either by means of patterns digitalization on a board of by a CAD/CAM system. Fig.4

Such machines are capable of cutting up to 3048 cm/min, with a +0.76 mm. tolerance. In a more specific manner and depending on the machine model available, as well as the type of material to be cut:

<u>SPEED</u>	<u>NUMBER OF PLYS</u>	<u>TYPE OF MATERIAL</u>
600 cm/min.	4	Unidirectional CF/EP
1000 cm/min.	4	CF/EP fabric
1500 cm/min.	10	K/EP fabric

Usage of such a system, currently used in most of the aircraft manufacturing compaies, yields the following results:

- a) Labor and production times reduction.
- b) Reduction of waste material percentage and rejections due to mistakes in cutting.
- c) Cutting repeatability and reliability.
- d) Cancellation of an exhaustive quality control.

Three cutting procedures are being used: reciprocating blade, water jet and laser. In the first case, the technology set up by the textile industry is followed, with several variances based on the oscillatory frequency (up to 5,500 strokes/min), which is represented in the stroke depth (number of plies simultaneously cut) and the quality of the cut. The two other processes, water jet and laser, in our opinion, still show problems, affecting in a higher or lower degree to the uncured material. In the first case, due to the water absorption possibility (always an undesirable condition), and in the second one, because it locally burns the material in the lips of the cut line. This process is being used by Grumman and McDonnell, the laser beam for cutting boron-epoxy, whereas British Aerospace is using the water jet for cutting carbon, fiber glass, Kevlar/epoxy. However, when the amount of material to be cut is high and needed to cut to net size, they are using the blade process method for the CF/epoxy.

Usage of Numerically controlled machines for cutting allows association of the patterns marking with a previously programmed identification resourcing to multiple heads. Basic equipments feature two or three servocontrolled axis.

4.3 Ply Pick Up, Lay Up and Molding

A great effort is being made since the 70's to obtain machines capable of sequentially picking these patterns according to the drawing and laying them on the molds in the required position. The main problems encountered are as follows:

- a) Lack of fabric plies stiffness.
- b) Variety and shape of the patterns cut.
- c) The necessity to remove the protective film the rolls of material are provided with and onto which the cutting operation is applied, after the lay up has been performed.
- d) Plies location and alignment accuracy.
- e) The requirement that the plies match the contour of the mould surface (debulking).

Currently, almost all of the assemblies made with fabric are made in a craftsmanship manner, by manually transporting the fabric plies, mylar and locating templates, spatulas and teflon rollers for manual compaction, and nylon bags, silicon or similar blankets for compaction under vacuum. All of the above operations are awkward, lack reliability and make the product expensive.

The stacking systems known up to this date are divided into two large categories: robots with special manipulators, picking and laying the fabric plies by means of suction, and lineal machines stacking the plies by using tapes and moving rollers. These systems are usually aided by optical and laser systems for location.

The results obtained up to this date are quite partial and short, but still there is a great effort on this purpose, though the tape laying machines development has slowed down this way. The Spanish industry, the same as that of the different industrial countries, is involved in several investigation programs, such as the FAMA program, wherein the composite material manufacturing companies are integrated.

4.4 Automated Tape Laying Fig. 5

The tapes, which are unidirectional fibers encased in a polymerizable matrix, with widths ranging from 75 mm. to 300 mm. (3 to 12 inches). Originally, this molding was performed by hand, strip by strip, to build up the laminate, this is an excessively labored and little reliable process, as $\pm 2^\circ$ variations in the lay up direction and gaps above 2 mm. within the same ply are considered as rejectable. Because of the above mentioned and the manufacturing schedules rate increase, it was necessary finding soon production systems not requiring so long production times and reliable. However, it was in the last third of the 80's that this system is being implemented in most of the aircraft manufacturing industries.

By the end of the 60's, the United States Air Force, aware of the problem, issued an assistance program through the AFML to General Dynamics and Conrad Corporation for the development of this type of machines. The first machines, with different modifications from the original one started production of the F-16 vertical and horizontal tail planes by the end of the 70's, yielding a manufacturing time savings of 58% with respect to the manual process. Since 1980 and basing on the experience of the above development, there are a certain number of companies starting development and manufacturing of new machines:

- Ingersoll (Rockford, Ill)
- Cincinnati Milacron (Cincinnati)
- Goldsworthy Engineering (Torrance, California)
- Vektronics (Carlsbad, California)

The two first companies have developed a family of machines wherein the header perform the cutting and locating functions, and it can be double or single. These machines are able to attain speeds up to 40 m/min. on contours up to 30° . The Goldsworthy-MFI machine is a two stages one (ACCESS/ATLAS), wherein the cutting and locating functions are segregated, both operations are then performed in parallel by a double header. An ACCESS machine cuts the tape and stores it in a cassette, the tape is then loaded into another machine, ATLAS, which lays and performs the compaction of the tape.

The family of machines developed by Vektronics is a two stages one, and as a difference from the other machines wherein the lay up tables are stationary, these tables are provided with a rotational movement, and the header laying the tape performs a single movement in the X axis direction.

Each machine is provided with a simulation software which allows viewing in graphics terminals the paths followed by the tapes, obtaining data on gaps and overlaps and optimizing the results. As a general rule, these machines lay previously cut tapes in the adequate direction and compact them under a 40 psi pressure.

C.A.S.A., after a detailed selection and election analysis based on the basic features parameters and the characteristics of the product to be manufactured, made the decision to purchase the Cincinnati Milacron machine. This company developed a simulation package consisting in:

- a) "ACRAPATH" Program: Batch operating program, it allows processing the geometrical shape and generating the tape laying paths, creating an APT source file with APT words and tape laying commands.

- b) "ACRAGRAPH" Program: Interactive program that allows viewing the tape laying process.
- c) "ACRAPOST" Program: Postprocessing program that generates the machine code for control from the APT source program.

The advantages presented by the usage of this type machines as opposed to the manual processes are as follows:

- a) Up to 86% hand labor savings with respect to the manual process. (The efficiency of these machines is about 10 pounds/hr. as an average, reaching a 22 pounds/hr. maximum.
- b) A 10% maximum waste of material.
- c) Repeatability in angles, gaps, orientation precision, obtaining optimum structures and removing inspection points.
- d) Uniform compaction pressure and deletion of the compaction and debulking operations typical of the manual lay up process.
- e) High process speed.
- f) Tape molding and location in position and with the same tension.

4.5 Curing Process

After the stacking or mold coating process has been performed, the resin is to be cured in order to obtain a stiff part. There exist two procedures to perform this operation: ovens or autoclaves, depending on whether a pressure cycle is to be applied or not. As for the ovens, the temperature control does not pose severe problems, but when a pressure cycle is associated to the thermal cycle, the condition gets more complicated.

The vacuum under the bag enveloping the part, the vessel pressure and the temperature have to be controlled during the autoclave cycles. This should be done assuring that the values stated in the standards, which precisely define the cycles and tolerances, are never exceeded. For this purpose, the part and tool heat carrying capabilities, as well as the tool heat transfer characteristics, design of which should be specially careful to prevent non uniform heating up at the same time that heat transfer to the part is favored, are to be considered.

The autoclaves usually are the critical items in the composite materials shop, this is due to two reasons: the cycle control, with the above stated problems, and the duration thereof (many hours), which require a careful planning and a good analysis of the maximum allowable loads, grouping the parts to receive the same process, as allowed by the equipment capacity.

The autoclaves feature control systems with ever increasing power computers and sophisticated software. Recently, there have been remarkable advances in the autoclave lines operation control and monitor centralizing, such as those currently found in the aerospace industry manufacturing shops, Fokker and C.A.S.A. in Europe, and Grumman and Boeing in the USA, are examples of this type of facilities.

As an example, the autoclaves C.A.S.A. has at the Getafe plant are provided with a centralized control, arranged in a hierarchy computerized architecture with different levels. Fig. 6.:

A central computer performs as a data base for the cycles and historical record for the parts processed, with the task of continuously monitoring the operation of each autoclave under the control thereof. At autoclave level, there is a local control receiving the program of the cycle to be performed and autonomous control, sending status reports on a periodic basis to a higher level. Contingencies are continuously recorded and the interface with the human operator allows a single person to take care of a facility provided with several autoclaves.

4.6 Cured Parts Machining

After the part has been obtained through the polymerization process the operations making up the solid condition material operations are performed, fig. 1, These operations are performed with machines which are similar to those used and developed for the metallic parts, except for the tools featuring special configurations.

The machining operations performed on composite materials are much more awkward and harmful because of the dust generated, as these are not performed by cutting or chip removal, but by abrasion. All of the machines are provided with a suction system for the dust generated.

Two types of equipment are used to automate these operations:

- a) Robots provided with specially developed heads.
- b) Gantry or column type numerically controlled machines.

If robots are used, special fixtures are utilized to guide the cutter thus allowing assuring an operation accuracy and repeatability, difficult to obtain if diamond cutters are used. They are not used if water jet is utilized, but for this purpose the part geometry has to allow the residual jet exit.

The numerically controlled machine has the advantage of a higher rigidity over the robot, no fixture is thus required to guide the cutting tool. Both systems programming and control benefit from the experience in the metal materials machining, being the CAD/CAM system applicable herein.

4.7 Non Destructive Testing:

The two types of non destructive testing currently used in the aircraft parts made from composite materials are the ultrasonic and X rays ones. However, currently there are another series of processes in use: holographic inspection, thermographic and acoustic emission are under study and development, existing very localized prototypes for very specific parts inspection.

Semi or totally automated equipments have been developed both for the ultrasonic and X ray inspection that facilitate such process. Below we are referring to the ultrasonic inspection, as the X ray inspection is an inspection process that in the laminated structure manufacturing is used in extreme cases only, and with the purpose of interpreting certain types of defects.

The ultrasonic inspection is based on ultrasonic waves passage through the assembly to be checked, with two different processes to be differentiated, depending on whether the wave is received on the surface opposing the one where it was input (through transmission process), or the reflected wave is received (reflection or pulse-echo process).

The ultrasonic waves input into the solid are attenuated by two means: Absorption and Scattering. Both of these are the cause of the attenuation, which is stated in dB/cm.

Absorption is an ultrasonic energy loss due to the oscillations in the lattice dislocation, transforming into heat. Dispersion is caused by the materials heterogeneity, this is specially relevant in the composite materials. Part inspection by ultrasonic means consists in the detection of the attenuation experienced by an ultrasonic emission within the material. Such attenuation is compared against reference values, which allows knowing the degree of compaction and the possible presence of foreign inclusions or objects. A coupling means is required between the emitter, receiver and part to allow wave input into the air. A water jet is usually used in the driven and automated equipments.

Figure / shows three generations of different equipments. The first generation, for flat or very slightly contoured parts, consist in a "pool" over which a double gantry moves, surrounding the part from above and below, which supports the emitters on one side and the receivers on the other. C.A.S.A. purchased this system in 1979 from Pentatron, and it incorporated a small microprocessor.

The second generation is made up by computer controlled gantries, these not only give an analogic reproduction of the attenuation thresholds, but they also provide a finer detail by grey shading or color ranges and signal pre-processing. Examples of these are the Sperry, McDonnell Douglas (AUS, Automatic Ultrasonic System), and SARA (Tecal, Spain) systems.

The third generation, was issued because of the need to inspect highly contoured parts or configurations with integrated longerons, wherefor system allowing control on a higher number of axis is required. Amongst the systems of this generation, the SIRO (Robotized Inspection System), Fig. 8, developed by C.A.S.A. in collaboration with several Spanish industries (ASEA, DYE) and Official Organizations (Madrid E.T.S.I.I. and Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas), and the "Computerized Ultrasonic Inspection" developed by Cincinnati Milacron, are to be highlighted.

The SIRO, a project started in March 1984, uses two robots, support for the ultrasonic equipments linked to a programming system associating the movement of the robots with the desired inspection paths. This system incorporates a computer assisted signal system that allows test result viewing in selectable colors shades. Fig 9. This inspection system is made up by the following systems:

ROBOTIZED INSPECTION SYSTEM (SIRO) Fig 9

a) Graphics system

- Defines the part geometry
- Generates the inspection program

b) Analysis processor

- Checks the inspection programs
 - Stores the programs and inspection data
- provides information

Graphic station

- Represents the ultrasonic data
- Marks the defects
- Issues reports

- | | | |
|---|----------|--|
| <p>c) <u>Local processor</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calculates, controls and times the robots position - Acquires the inspection data | receives | <p><u>Ultrasonic system</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Handles the signal - Triggers acquisition |
| <p>d) <u>Robots</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Position the transducers | | |
| <p>e) <u>Frame</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positions the part. | | |

4.8 Other operations:

We would like to incorporate herein, in addition to a whole series of operations the machining, automation and robotizing of which is being, or will be, developed in the conventional industry and can be transferred to the composite materials (X ray equipments, riveting equipments, painting, guided transport, storage, etc.), those operations that are developed because of the requirements of the process itself.

We would like to refer to the following machines without trying to fully describe them:

- Filament winding systems.
- Systems or machines dedicated for certain designs (helicopter blades, radomes, etc.).
- Rework syems or machines.
- NC machines, core carving.
- Non metallic core forming and stabilization.
- Honeycomb blocks stretching machines.
- Non rigid items transport systems.
- Non polymerized formed items storage systems.
- Forming systems.
- etc.

5 INTEGRATION

The machining, automation and in some cases robotizing of the above described operations, together with secondary operations (tool repair, transport) allows integration of all of them in a certain area to create segregated cells controlled with the assistance of computerized systems, to manufacture composite materials items or assemblies, ready for the final assembly.

6 APPLICATION TO THE A330/340 HORIZONTAL TAIL PLANE

Basing on the experience obtained with the manufacturing of the A-320 horizontal tail plane (the first commercial aircraft horizontal tail plane fully manufactured in carbon fiber), the A-330/340 horizontal tail plane design was started. This new plane also is an integral fuel tank.

In this case, the logical process to allow manufacturing automation was followed.

6.1 Design:

A joint design was made in order to obtain the most optimized weight structure and as cheap as possible to manufacture.

In order to minimize the assembly hours, a highly integrated design was selected, that is, each item is provided with stiffeners and systems to secure them onto the surrounding items built into the part.

This design philosophy highly reduces the number of parts to be assembled and therefore the time required for assembly.

Each part design was agreed between the design and manufacturing groups selecting the optimum solution for each of them.

6.2 STRUCTURE DESCRIPTION

The structural configuration is shown in the figure 10,11.

The tail plane is made up by a center metallic box and two side boxes fully made from carbon fiber/epoxy.

The side box is made up by two skins made from tape with stiffeners, rib attachments and spar attachments built into the part on a base skin.

Front and rear spars are also made from tape and feature built in stiffeners.

The 21 box ribs are manufactured from fabric and feature built in stiffeners and rear spar attaching angle.

The fuel tank area extends up to 8 m. out of the 9 m. span of this side box.

Four leading edge ribs manufactured from C/F fabric and 3 leading edge sections manufactured from C/F fabric and Nomex core are secured onto the box.

The trailing edge features 7 ribs/elevator rotation fitting, 2 actuator bars and 5 auxiliary ribs manufactured from C/F fabric. The trailing edge covers and the elevator are made in a sandwich structure with C/F skins and Nomex core.

Attachment to the center metallic box is simple shear by means of titanium bolts. This attachment was found the one providing the best price to weight selection of all of those evaluated.

6.3 Manufacturing

The most representative item in the A-330/340 horizontal tail plane are the skins, which have the stringers, and the spar, rib and longerons attachment built in a single part. This item is manufactured in a single autoclave cycle, i.e., cocured, and the tooling system used is the advanced modular one, whereby the stiffeners compaction is obtained through the differential expansion between the aluminum blocks and a C/F base Fig. 12.

- Hot forming Fig. 13

After the flat laminates have been cut to the final dimension, they are formed to the required shape by means of the hot forming process.

The Convac II hot forming machine, fully developed by C.A.S.A., has been provided with a fully automated operation to facilitate the loading and unloading tasks.

The parts that have been completed and formed, but still uncured, are stored on special fixtures in the "smart" refrigerated store until they are installed on the base skin for cure.

- Curing process

Assembly of all of the uncured parts on the aluminum modules and the whole assembly on the base skin is also automated by means of high precision turning racks and movement and location devices.

Tools design greatly facilitates the vacuum bagging.

Autoclave control is fully automated and computer monitored. The autoclave is also provided with nitrogen facility for inert atmosphere curing and fire prevention.

The part demolding system is currently being automated developing a head for it capable of securing the aluminum modules and smoothly remove them.

Tool cleaning and mold release agents application is also being automated.

- Non destructive testing

With the development of the automatic equipment of ultrasonic inspection called "SARA" made by a spanish company, we save a lot of time in that operation compared with the old equipment used before.

- Triming

CASA cut the skins to the final shape with the CNC machine "JOBS" specifically developed to trim composite materials with dust absorption system.

The trim operation is made automatically assuring a repetitivity in the final shape.

- Conclusions

With the actual design of composite structures and the manufacturing processes applied, the cost of these structures is competitive with the metallic ones if we take in account weight reduction and the avoid of corrosion and fatigue problems.

The only way to reach a more competitive cost is the automation of the manufacturing processes but it is possible with a proper design and a minimum number of parts

to manufacture because the big investments required. The trends is to a high automated and integrated composite facilities to manufacture very large parts.

With the new processes applied to aerospace industry like "RTM, RIM" is possible to implement automation to little parts also because the investments required are lower that ones for the contact method

The main problem remains the elevated cost of the raw material.

FIG. 0

MCAIR EVOLUTION IN COMPOSITE APPLICATION

1967

F-4

41 RAD RUDDERS
80 IN SERVICE EVALUATION RUDDERS

1978

AV-8B

WING TORQUE BOX - 71% GRAPHITE/EPOXY
FLAPS
AILERONS
WING TIP TANK
OUTRIGGER FAIRING
OVERWING FAIRING
ENGINE ACCESS DOORS

1970

F-15

EMPENNAGE - PRODUCTION
SPEEDBRAKE - PRODUCTION

1975

F-18

WING BRIMS
TRAILING EDGE
FLAPS
LEADING EDGE EXTENSION
SPEEDBRAKE
HORIZONTAL STABILATOR
VERTICAL TAIL
RUDDER
COVERS AND ACCESS DOORS

■ BORON/EPOXY
▨ GRAPHITE/EPOXY

PROGRAM STATUS	% COMPOSITE IN STRUCTURE
A) PRODUCTION	
F 14A	0.8
F 15	1.6
F 16	2.5
F 18	9.5
AV 8B	26.0
B) DEVELOPMENT	
ATF	40 - 50
ADVANCED V/STOL	50 - 60

FIG. 0

fig 1

Figura 2

TECHNOLOGY	CUTTING SPEED	MAXIMUM NUMBER OF PLYS	PERCENTAGE OF MATERIAL WASTE
Hand cutting (1)	282 cm/min. 140 cm/min.	1 4	20 - 30%
Die cutting (2)	7500 cm/min	>> 4	12 - 20%
Automated cutting (3)	600 - 1500 cm/min.	>> 4	12 - 15

- (1) Speeds shown are for 1 ply of CF/EP and FG/EP. This is reduced by a 20% for the Kevlar. The maximum number of plies for the Kevlar is 2, and the cutting speed is 115 cm/min.
- (2) Assuming approximately a 25 m. perimeter for the cutter.
- (3) The most used standard speed is 800 cm/min., which considering the accelerations and decelerations because of change in the cutting direction, and on an optimized "nesting", means an average between 500 and 600 cm/min.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4
CAD/CAM system ply cutting machine
Manufactured by Induyco (Spain)

Fig. 5
Illescas Plant Tape Laying Area

CASA Getafe: Autoclaves

Fig. 6

SISTEMA DE INSPECCION SIRO (PATENTE CASA)

FIG.-8

Limite inferior del rango : 15
Limite superior del rango : 90

Figura 9

A-330/340 HTP TORSION BOX

Fig 10

TAILPLANE SKIN

DETAIL

Fig 12

CONVAC II

Fig 13